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Effect of temperature on impact behaviour of polyamide 6/woven basalt fibres laminates

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Outline

- Introduction

 - Basalt : properties and applications

 - Aim of the work

- Experimentals

 - Sample preparation

 - Characterization techniques

- Results and Discussion

- Conclusive remarks

Basalt

- High strength and high modulus fiber
- **High temperature resistance and good light resistance**
- Good fatigue and corrosion resistance properties
- Easy to handle and process
- **Can be recycled**
- No need for special processing equipment
- Exhibit no health and safety risks
- Better chemical resistance than e-glass

Property	Basalt	E-glass
Diameter[μm]	8.63	9 - 13
Density[kgm^{-3}]	2733	2540
Softening temp. [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	960	840

Manufacturing cost of basalt fibers is higher than E-glass but less than S-glass, aramid or carbon fibers.

Typical composition of basalt fiber vs. E-glass fiber		
Chemical components	Basalt Weight %	E-Glass Weight %
SiO_2 (silica)	58	55
Al_2O_3 (alumina)	17	15
Fe_2O_3 (ferric oxide)	10	0.3
CaO	8	18
MgO	4	3
Na ₂ O	2.5	0.8
TiO_2	1.1	-
K_2O	0.8	0.2
B_2O_3	-	7
F	-	0.3

	Basalt	E-Glass
Tensile Strength, MPa	3000 – 4840	3100 – 3800
Elastic Modulus, GPa	93 – 110	72.5 – 75.5
Elongation at break, %	3.1 – 6.0	5
Specific Gravity	2.65 - 2.80	2.50 – 2.62
Max Temp. of application, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	650	380
Melting Temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$	1470	1120

Main aim of the research

Studying the influence of temperature on the impact behaviour of composite laminates based on a polyamide 6 and reinforced with woven-basalt fibers

Raw materials and laminates preparation

The matrix:

Nylon 6 (**PA6**), Lanxess Durethan B30S-000000 (MFI@260 °C, 5 kg: 102 g/10 min).

The reinforcement:

A plain woven basalt fabrics **BS** (weight: 210 g/m²) from Incotology (GmbH)

Composite laminates were prepared by a typical film stacking procedure by which stacks of alternated layers of plastic films and woven fibers are subjected to a hot compression step under pre-optimized conditions. Operating in this way, samples constituted by 18 layers, symmetrically stacked with respect to the middle plane, were obtained with a thickness equal to 2.90 ± 0.01 mm (BS/PA6).

Characterization Techniques

Low velocity impact testing

Instrument: INSTRON CEAST 9350 Drop Tower
Specimen support: according to ASTM D7136M
Striker: 22 kN Strain-Gauge, 20 mm hemispheric
Total mass: 5.41 kg (up to 30 J) and 10.41 kg (60J)
Impact energies: 5, 20, 30 and 60 J
Test temperatures: 40, 80 and 100°C

Dynamic-Mechanical Analysis

Instrument: TA-DMA Q800
Test: Single Cantilever mode
Frequency : 1 Hz
Heating rate rate of 3°C/min from 23 to 100°C.

Impact results

	T=40 °C			T=80 °C			T=100 °C		
U [J]	F _{max} [N]	d _{Fmax} [mm]	U _a [J]	F _{max} [N]	d _{Fmax} [mm]	U _a [J]	F _{max} [N]	d _{Fmax} [mm]	U _a [J]
5	2510.40	3.95	1.82	2116.83	4.75	2.13	2001.57	4.74	2.05
20	5525.49	7.56	11.66	4743.67	8.93	12.70	3918.81	9.36	12.46
30	6089.03	8.99	20.37	5295.80	11.52	21.57	4807.15	11.53	19.77
60	6516.36	10.59	50.56	6319.57	12.23	52.93	5658.94	13.09	54.34

By increasing the temperature, a significant decrease in the slope of the initial section of the curve and an increase of the deformation in correspondence of the maximum point are evident.

No differences in terms of slope, deflection and absorbed energy were found between 80 and 100°C.

The absorbed energy normalized with respect to the total impact energy (U_a/U_{tot}) shows an increasing trend with both the impact energy and the temperature (all over the examined thermal range).

Dynamic-mechanical behaviour

Results being processed

Conclusive remarks

Under the same impact energy, the increase in temperature shifts and lowers the maximum of the force-deflection curve to the right, ie it reduces the maximum contact force and the energy absorbed at this point but increases the corresponding deflection. This effect fades for temperatures above a certain threshold value (probably coinciding with the heat deflection temperature of the matrix).

As the temperature increases, in addition to the expected reduction in the impact resistance of the composite, the section of the curve preceding its maximum point appears more and more smooth. In other words, despite the increase in temperature the dynamic resistance decreases, it is likely that the delaminated area decreases which leads to a different way of using the absorbed energy. But this aspect is still being tested by non-destructive methods.

Dynamic-mechanical results ...

Thank you very much for listening

Any question?